

D3.2

IN SITU MEASUREMENTS DATA COLLECTION REPORT

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LANDMARC

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Short Summary of results

The document provides an overview of the in-situ measurements data explaining why and how this data (forest biomass and biodiversity with FieldMap; Forest biomass monitoring; Soil analysis and Eddy Covariance flux data) were collected, processed and used in the frame of various deliverables and outputs of some LANDMARC case studies to establish the baseline and measure change at a wide range of spatial and temporal scales in order to measure biomass and LMTs and their impact as net sinks.

Evidence of accomplishment

This report includes an overview of the in-situ data collection in the different case studies and countries and a summary of the main results.

- Preface

Negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and net zero emissions policy scenarios. To date most climate actions have focused on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfil the Paris Agreement and meet the world's climate goals, research, policy and markets are increasingly looking at negative emission solutions.

This is why the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work together in order to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assess the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Map their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

LANDMARC is an interdisciplinary consortium with expertise from ecology, engineering, climate sciences, global carbon cycle, soil sciences, satellite earth observation sciences, agronomy, economics, social sciences, and business. There is a balanced representation of partners from academia, SMEs, and NGOs from the EU, Africa, Asia, and the Americas, which ensures a wide coverage of LMTs operating in different contexts (e.g., climates, land-use practices, socio-economic etc.) and spatial scales.

The LANDMARC project consortium:

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Disclaimer:

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1. Overview

The objective of this deliverable is to provide an overview of the in-situ measurement data collected in the LANDMARC project. The project aims to monitor and characterize soil factors and microbial diversity, across Land-Based Mitigation Technologies and Practices (LMTs) and evaluate forest biomass and Eddy Covariance flux data using various tools such as FieldMap and ETLook model. The integration of these tools is aimed at improving the precision and accuracy of monitoring, thereby enhancing the evaluation of LMT effectiveness.

The primary aim of these measurements is to establish baselines and track changes of LMT applications across different spatial and temporal scales. By collecting accurate and real-time data through in-situ measurements, we gain valuable insights into the dynamics of biomass related to LMT activities. This information is vital for evaluating the effectiveness of LMTs as mitigation and net sink potentials. While in-situ measurements tools have certain limitations in terms of temporal continuity and spatial coverage, Task 2.2 “Collecting complementary data and information” of the project involves collecting supplementary secondary available in-situ data. This additional data collection aims to complement and enhance the insights gained from our primary measurements, addressing any gaps and broadening the scope of our analysis.

Each of the five techniques used by the WP3 earth observation partners including soil analysis, above ground biomass and gas flux measurements, serves a specific purpose within the project. For example, soil analysis encompasses the assessment of chemical, physical, and biological properties with the use of molecular biology techniques, including the determination of organic carbon percentage and the composition and diversity of microbial communities. Special emphasis is placed on microorganisms associated with greenhouse gas production. The use of FieldMap software also enables efficient inventory and analysis of forest and agricultural data in forestry and agroforestry case studies, facilitating the assessment of forest biomass and biodiversity. This software can also be complemented by forest biomass monitoring involves traditional manually "in-situ" data collection of selected forest parameters to determine carbon deposits. This includes measuring aerial biomass, radial biomass, decomposing organic matter, dead wood, and soil organic matter. Furthermore, existing Eddy Covariance flux data from South Africa and other locations in Europe were collected to calibrate the ETLook algorithm developed by eLEAF. This step ensures accurate estimation of evapotranspiration and other related variables using remote sensing data. Overall, the combination of these in-situ measurement tools contributes to a comprehensive understanding of soil biodiversity, forest biomass, and carbon fluxes, supporting informed decision-making and effective evaluation of LMTs and guide to evaluate and calibrate models to give robustness to upscaling exercises within the LANDMARC project.

The in-situ measurements data is being supported in a subset of the areas (depending on their size) by the remote sensing techniques to help as a smart soil sampling strategy (LANDMAR article, 2020).

The selection based on satellites to collect soil samples for chemical, physical and biological soil and vegetation data helps to connect the data to the LMT and its effectiveness in several case studies. We then complement in-situ data results with remote sensing data. This enables the characterization and identification of different land uses in the case studies and LMTs and within each of them different management zones that will allow a faster and more accurate selection of soil sampling sites. The correlations between in-situ measurements and remote sensing data enhance the depth of our analysis. For instance, in Case Study 16 (Montado/Dehesa, Portugal and Spain), we have conducted a correlation analysis between microbial results and chlorophyll fluorescence data, assessing their relationship to crop water availability and carbon sequestration using Agrosider's remote sensing technique. In Case Study 5 (Integrated soil fertility management, Kenya), we've established links between soil processes, particularly nitrogen cycling, and N₂O flux measurements.

Additional correlations are being explored within the microbial analysis and results obtained from other tools. For example, our upcoming plan includes an analysis of microbial data from Case Study 3 (Forest Management, Germany) with the aim of correlating it with FieldMap results, providing insights into carbon sequestration within trees and soil in this specific case study. Furthermore, we're in the process of linking the collected eddy-covariance data from Case Study 2 (Peatland rewetting – Onlanden location, the Netherlands) to soil microbial processes related to carbon dynamics, encompassing CO₂ and methane in the area. However, we will not discuss the combination of in-situ and remote sensing data in this deliverable since the emphasis is on in-situ data collection (see details in D3.3: Prototype model observation system).

The LANDMARC project involved the utilization of diverse in-situ techniques across different case studies worldwide. The objective is to monitor soil biodiversity and health and establish connections with carbon sequestration, thus quantifying the impacts of various LMTs. In order to estimate mitigation and negative emissions as well as provide support for LMT strategic planning and decision-making, a combination of satellite observations and in-situ data collection from soil, water, atmosphere, and vegetation at varying spatial resolutions was integrated. The outcomes of this approach are documented in D3.3, which focuses on the Prototype model observation system. This deliverable highlights the integration of innovative and developed techniques, particularly in the Netherlands and Portugal/Spain case studies.

2. In-situ measurements data collection

The following table provides a summary of the in-situ measurements conducted as part of Work Package 3 within the LANDMARC project. This overview includes 16 distinct case studies covering various countries across the globe. Each case study is detailed, specifying the available data and parameters measured and identifying the responsible institution assigned with its storage.

Table 1. Overview of the collection of in-situ measurements data.

CS No.	Case study	Country	Extra Location info	In situ parameter (what)*	Storage
1	Agroforestry**	The Netherlands	Location 1: Helmond (2021)	Physic-chemical factors Microbial analysis	Bioclear earth
2	Peatland rewetting	The Netherlands	Location 1: Plaudiculture (2021)	Physic-chemical factors Microbial analysis	Bioclear earth Bioclear earth
			Location 2: Onlanden (2023)	Eddy covariance (data from Onlanden area provided by third party (Wageningen University))	eLEAF
			Location 3: Blauzaam (2023)**		
3	Forest Management	Germany		Physic-chemical factors Microbial analysis	Bioclear earth Bioclear earth
				Forest biomass and biodiversity	Ambienta
4	Reduced tillage	Switzerland	-	Physic-chemical factors	Bioclear earth
5	Organic cropping	Switzerland	-	Physic-chemical factors	Bioclear earth
6	Fire forest management	Venezuela	No in-situ technologies applied mainly due to lack of access to land due to social-political challenges		
7	Eddy Covariance Flux measurements	Burkina*** Faso		Physic-chemical factors Microbial analysis	Bioclear earth Bioclear earth
8	Eddy Covariance Flux measurements	South Africa		Eddy covariance	eLEAF
9	Integrated soil fertility management	Kenya	4 sites (Aludeka, Embu, Machanga, Sidada) Microbial only Sidada	Physic-chemical factors Microbial analysis	Bioclear earth
10	Reforestation/peatlands restoration	Canada	Location 1: Sampling in different points (2023)	Physic-chemical factors Microbial analysis	Bioclear earth
11	Biochar	Sweden	No in-situ technologies applied due to changes as biochar is an 'add on technology' rather than a direct land use technology		
12	Biogas	Indonesia	Location 1 (2022)	Physic-chemical factors Microbial analysis	Bioclear earth
			Location 2 (2023)**		
13	Agroforestry**	Spain	Location 1: Spanish National Forest Inventory (2022)	Physic-chemical factors Microbial analysis	Bioclear earth Bioclear earth
				Forest biomass and biodiversity	Ambienta
14	Sustainable coffee and pepper production	Vietnam	The application of in-situ technologies for soil sampling faced a delivery challenge of soil sampling kits in Vietnam, impacting the study's implementation.		

CS No.	Case study	Country	Extra Location info	In situ parameter (what)*	Storage
15	Sustainable rice production	Nepal	Sampling in rice fields (2022)	Physic-chemical factors Microbial analysis	Bioclear earth Bioclear earth
16	Montado/ Dehesa**	Portugal & Spain	Location 1: Sampling in Pasture of Portugal (2021)	Physic-chemical factors Microbial analysis	Bioclear earth Bioclear earth
			Location 2: Spanish National Forest Inventory (2022)	Physic-chemical factors Microbial analysis	Bioclear earth Bioclear earth
				Forest biomass and biodiversity	Ambienta
18	Organic farming**	Ukraine***		Physic-chemical factors Microbial analysis	Bioclear earth Bioclear earth
19	Forest fire	Australia	No in-situ technologies applied: mainly desk research case study as proof of concept for Solar-induced Florescence (SIF) application.		
20	Restauration	China		No in-situ technologies applied: mainly desk research case study as proof of concept for Solar-induced Florescence (SIF) application.	KNMI

*: In situ parameter (what): for each physical chemical factors measured will be dependent of the laboratory of each country. However, almost each case study has measurements such as: pH, N, C, P, K.

** : Soil sampling done through smart soil sampling strategy (satellites)

***: Sampling will be done between the period of November and December 2023.

3. In-situ measurements main results

In this section, we present a summary of the in-situ measurement results, which encompass data gathered through various techniques, including Microbial analysis, FieldMap, and Eddy covariance analyses for each case study listed in Table 2. To enhance reader comprehension, we begin by providing instructions and additional information for effectively interpreting the results presented in Table 2 for each technique. Following this, we delve into a more detailed explanation of the treatments administered at each pilot site, where various combinations of in-situ measurements are being utilized.

3.1 Soil analysis

In the soil analysis, the goal is to provide a straightforward explanation of the microbial results found exclusively in Table 2. While the microbial data is extensive, we'll focus on key indicators of soil health and specific genera and genes related to the nitrogen cycle and carbon sequestration. One crucial focus is the genus *Bacillus* and the plant growth-promoting bacteria (PGPB). PGPB play a vital role in enhancing plant growth and aiding in soil restoration. They achieve this by secreting various helpful compounds and hormones, fixing nitrogen in the soil, and making other nutrients more accessible to plants through mineral dissolution (Poria et al., 2022). PGPB is a diverse group, encompassing different bacterial genera, including *Bacillus*. Another important group, the mycorrhizal fungi, plays a crucial role in enhancing plant nutrient and water uptake from the soil. Additionally, they significantly improve plant tolerance to various environmental stresses. This information is essential to help farmer to improve their soil and crop health. PGPB and mycorrhizal fungi can boost crop growth and make plants more resilient to challenging conditions, ultimately leading to better yields and healthier crops.

Furthermore, in this deliverable, our microbial analysis results primarily focus on the nitrogen (N) and carbon (C) cycles. The application of nitrogen fertilizers in agricultural fields significantly impacts these processes, leading to an increased production of N_2O , a potent greenhouse gas (Lu et al., 2006). On the other hand, biological nitrogen fixation plays a vital role in providing nitrogen to the ecosystem. Our Table 2 results will shed light on N_2O emissions and nitrogen fixation, which are vital pathways for understanding what is happening in the nitrogen cycle. As for the carbon cycle, in a simplified manner, carbon moves from the atmosphere to the soil through various organisms, such as photosynthesizing plants and microbes. These microbes convert atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO_2) into organic material. The fixed carbon is later released back into the atmosphere through various pathways, mainly due to the respiration of different types of organisms. (Lu et al., 2005; Trumbore et al., 2006). Methane is produced by certain microorganisms, while others, called methanotrophs, consume it. The balance between methane-producing and methane-consuming microbes in different soil layers determines the net amount of methane in the atmosphere (Gougoulis et al., 2014).

In the context of land-based mitigation techniques, our study of the microbial nitrogen and carbon cycles, along with soil health, allows us to better grasp how different management or soil amendments affect both greenhouse gas emissions and the overall well-being of the soil. This insight is valuable for making informed decisions on land management to reduce emissions and enhance soil health and ecosystem vitality.

3.2 Above ground biomass

Forestry measurements empowered by FieldMap technology mark a significant leap forward in both the efficiency of data collection and the quality of results. The primary aim of utilizing FieldMap technology is to create precise local and species-specific dendrometric¹ models (Diéguez Aranda et al., 2023). When combined with pertinent forest cubing equations², these models yield dependable and well-validated data regarding the total timber volumes within a designated forest area (Diéguez Aranda et al., 2023). Subsequently, through the application of conversion equations, these timber volumes can be transformed into units representing stored carbon or carbon dioxide (CO₂), offering valuable insights into the forest's environmental impact and mitigation potential.

Firstly, for each forest system under examination, a dasometric³ study is conducted (Diéguez Aranda et al., 2023). This study assesses the appropriate sampling intensity, which involves determining the number of inventory plots. These plots are typically circular and have a fixed radius. The sampling intensity is determined by considering an established relative error and accounting for the number of distinct strata based on various vegetation units within the forest system, if applicable. This analysis is crucial for guaranteeing that field measurements accurately represent and align with the expected results.

Secondly, on-site sampling of the established inventory plots is performed. This involves measuring the diameters of all inventoriable trees, specifically the larger trees meeting a certain standard diameter, typically known as the diameter at breast height (DBH). Additionally, the total heights (Ht) of selected representative trees from each tree species, characterized as healthy, straight, and exemplary representatives of their respective groups, are recorded. The primary objective here is to construct local regression models based on the DBH-Ht variables for each tree species found in the various case studies. Furthermore, a brief assessment is conducted to document the silvicultural status of the plot. This assessment aids in characterizing the forest system under study, taking into account factors such as the forest stand's structure, the specific composition of tree species, the quantity of

¹ Dendrometry encompasses measuring an individual tree's dimensions, studying its shape, and determining its volume. Commonly measured parameters to characterize tree size are height and diameter at breast height.

² Cubing equation refers to cubing equations and models available, each tailored for different tree species, regions, and forest conditions. The choice of which cubing equation to use depends on the specific study, the tree species in question, and the forest characteristics being analyzed.

³ Dasometry refers to the part of forest science that deals with the application of statistical methods in the search for solutions to problems associated with the existence, growth and management of forests.

biomass per species, and the phytosociological relationships among different vegetation strata. During the data processing phase, the DBH-Ht variables are utilized in allometric equations tailored to each species. This step serves the initial goal of obtaining accurate and dependable estimates of timber volumes for each plot, which can later be extrapolated to encompass the entire forest area.

Finally, these timber volumes are converted into estimates of stored carbon and carbon dioxide (CO₂). This is done with the aim of quantifying the carbon storage in each forest system investigated within the case studies, contributing valuable insights into the forest's environmental impact. FieldMap technology aids in the assessment of forests, enabling precise measurement and modeling of timber volumes and associated carbon storage. By quantifying the carbon sequestration potential of a forest area, FieldMap facilitates a deeper understanding of their role in CO₂ emissions reduction efforts, ultimately contributing to informed forest management strategies with environmental benefits.

3.3 Gas flux measurements

Eddy Covariance (EC) flux towers are equipped with instruments tailored for in situ monitoring of the intricate interactions between ecosystems and the atmosphere. These towers play a critical role in quantifying exchanges of gases, energy, and momentum. They excel in measuring energy fluxes, particularly latent heat flux for estimating evapotranspiration, and gas fluxes related to the net ecosystem exchange of carbon dioxide, often at high temporal resolutions, such as hourly or half-hourly intervals. The fundamental principle behind eddy covariance systems lies in recognizing that wind does not move in a unidirectional manner but exhibits complex, three-dimensional circular patterns. As the wind flows, it carries with it water vapor and various gases, including carbon dioxide. Precisely measuring the speed and characteristics of these swirling air masses in all three dimensions enables the determination of the net exchange of these gases between the Earth's surface and the atmosphere. Concurrently, a gas analyzer is employed to quantify the concentration of water vapor (and other gases) present in the air at a given moment. By examining the covariance between the movement of the air mass and its composition, these systems calculate heat and water fluxes, along with carbon dioxide fluxes. These calculations are foundational for deriving essential variables such as sensible heat flux (H), latent heat flux (LE), and evapotranspiration (ET).

Net ecosystem production (NEP) is a critical metric derived from eddy covariance (EC) measurements, representing the net carbon balance within ecosystems. This concept of NEP, which integrates measurements from EC systems, contributes to a comprehensive understanding of carbon dynamics in ecosystems, connecting the flux measurements to ecosystem carbon balances. It's defined as the difference between gross primary production (GPP) and net ecosystem respiration (Re). Positive NEP values typically indicate carbon emissions, often occurring at night when respiration exceeds photosynthesis. Conversely, negative values signify carbon uptake by ecosystems, which is common during daylight hours when photosynthesis is active. The relationships among different components of ecosystem productivity are described by three theoretical identities:

$$Re = Ra + Rh$$

$$NPP = GPP - Ra$$

$$NEP = NPP - Rh = GPP - Re$$

To estimate these components, particularly Re , models are employed under conditions where GPP is known to be zero, such as nighttime or low-light periods. These models describe respiration as a function of environmental variables, like temperature. Once a model for Re is established, it can be applied to daytime conditions. Subtracting the modeled daytime Re from the directly measured daytime NEP provides an estimate of GPP. While EC provides direct estimates of GPP and Re , determining autotrophic respiration (Ra) often necessitates additional methods or assumptions. In many ecosystems, Ra is estimated as a fixed fraction of GPP. Therefore, once GPP is known, Ra (and consequently, net primary production, NPP) can be estimated.

In the context of land-based mitigation techniques (LMTs), the three theoretical identities connecting Gross Primary Production (GPP), Net Primary Production (NPP), Autotrophic Respiration (Ra), and Net Ecosystem Production (NEP) provide a robust framework to understand and optimize CO₂ emissions reduction strategies. These identities help assess the carbon balance in ecosystems, enabling better management of carbon sequestration potential and the development of targeted LMTs for effective CO₂ reduction.

3.4 Table 2: Key Findings from In-Situ Measurements

After reviewing the preceding guide for data interpretation, we summarize the techniques applied in each case study that utilized in-situ measurements and had initial results. It is important to highlight that the choice of technologies applied in different countries was influenced by a combination of factors. Specific access to gas flux equipment played a role in some cases, limiting it to only several case studies with existing equipment. The FieldMap technology is a specialized software only employed by one partner, which limited it to several case studies where the partner could travel to case study regions and apply the technology. Additionally, soil sampling was carried out by case study partners, enabling its use in nearly every case study where access to plots was available, and where case study leads were willing and able to take samples. These considerations shaped the selection and deployment of technologies based on resource availability and collaborative capacity.

Below are descriptions of select case studies to enhance the readability and understanding of Table 2:

Agroforestry (Netherlands):

Soil microbial sampling: Satellite-based methods and imagery were used to pinpoint sampling locations across three distinct sites within agroforestry systems that had once been conventional

monoculture croplands. Our emphasis was placed on selecting areas that best represented the plots for sampling. These agroforestry cropland systems were compared with adjacent monoculture cropland systems, including a potato plantation and the intermediate area situated between the agroforestry and the monoculture zones. These study sites are situated in Alphen, North Brabant, Netherlands.

FieldMap: not done for this case study.

Eddy Covariance Flux measurements: not done for this case study.

Peatlands rewetting (Netherlands):

Soil microbial sampling:

Location paludiculture: In May 2021, soil sampling and microbial analysis was conducted at the paludiculture site. soil sampling and microbial analysis were carried out without employing a smart soil sampling approach. This deviation from the smart sampling method was necessitated by the scale of the pilot project under consideration. As a result, the sampling process followed conventional, standard procedures for soil sampling, which are necessary for subsequent microbial analysis. The sampling efforts covered rewetted peatland, encompassing both soil and water samples, as well as a reference site located in a degraded peatland. The pilot site, situated in Swinkels, Netherlands, was dedicated to the implementation of paludiculture. This involved maintaining a high water table and blocking drainage ditches while cultivating cattails. The project encompassed activities such as infilling the central drainage ditch, constructing low peat bunds, implementing subsoil irrigation, planting cattails, and taking measures to protect young plants from geese grazing. Please note that data is not yet available for the locations in Onlanden and Blauzaam.

FieldMap: not done for this case study.

Eddy Covariance Flux measurements: data are collected for the Onlanden case study provided by Wageningen University.

Integrated soil fertility management (Kenya):

Soil microbial sampling: In November 2021, soil sampling and microbial analysis were conducted in a subset of treatments from a 16 year old long-term trial (in Sidada) with a randomized split plot design with three replicates. The study involved three different treatments (control without organic inputs, farmyard manure (FYM) addition, and maize stover addition at $1.2 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) with and without the addition of mineral N fertilizer ($120 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ season}^{-1}$). Samples were taken at three different time points after the organic resource addition (37, 40 and 46 days). Fluxes of CO_2 and N_2O were measured at the same time period (chamber method).

FieldMap: not done for this case study.

Eddy Covariance Flux measurements: not done for this case study.

Biogas (Indonesia):

Soil microbial sampling: In October 2022, soil sampling and microbial analysis were carried out without employing a smart soil sampling approach. This deviation from the smart sampling method was necessitated by the scale of the pilot project under consideration (Location 1). Samples were taken from five different farms, including agroforestry of cacao and jackfruit, non-organic arabica coffee, agroforestry of organic arabica coffee with sapodilla, robusta coffee, and pongamia tree. In May 2023, another soil sampling and microbial analysis were conducted with the soil smart sampling approach (Location 2). Samples were taken from five different farms for the following treatments: non-organic arabica coffee, agroforestry of organic arabica coffee, and pongamia tree.

FieldMap: not done for this case study.

Eddy Covariance Flux measurements: not done for this case study.

Agroforestry (Spain):

Soil microbial sampling: Satellite-based methods were used to indicate sampling points. Samples were taken from three different areas with various treatments, including control agriculture, control forest, soil from tree rows, soils from between trees, and soils from shrub rows (only in area 3) and shrub trees (only in area 3).

FieldMap: During the spring of 2022, in situ forest and biodiversity measurement work was carried out, which will provide ground truth information to other techniques used, such as remote sensing, in three pilot farms in Extremadura (Spain). FieldMap technology is used to measure plant biodiversity and existing biomass, obtain the main tree height diameter model, and generate the necessary information to transform into biomass stored C values, in the three reforestation farms of degraded agricultural land, several years after reforestation.

Eddy Covariance Flux measurements: not done for this case study.

Forest management (Germany):

Soil microbial sampling: Satellite-based methods were used to indicate sampling points. Samples were taken from three different stratas from managed and unmanaged forest in Lübeck (Germany) provided by OEKO from under tree rows and soils from between trees.

FieldMap: forest and biodiversity measurement work, which will provide ground truth information to other techniques such as remote sensing, was carried out on a pilot forest in Lübeck (Germany) provided by OEKO. The soil sampling FieldMap technology is used to measure plant biodiversity and existing biomass, obtain the main tree height diameter model, and generate the necessary information to transform into biomass C values in the peri-urban forest where different strata have been detected depending on the structure of the forest stand.

Eddy Covariance Flux measurements: not done for this case study.

South Africa:

Soil microbial sampling: not done for this case study.

FieldMap: not done for this case study.

Eddy covariance Flux measurements: data collection was carried out in the South African case study, involving five distinct towers: GF-K, GF-S, NT-A1, NT-A2, and NT-P. These towers drew data from different sources, including EFTEON, University of Pretoria, and University of KwaZulu-Natal, each capturing a variety of vegetation types. These encompass the Karoo, Savanna, Hass avocado orchard, Pecan orchard, and mixed cultivar regions.

Sustainable rice production (Nepal):

Soil microbial sampling: In December 2021, soil sampling and microbial analysis were carried out without employing a smart soil sampling approach. This deviation from the smart sampling method was necessitated by the scale of the pilot project under consideration. The soil were targeting the following treatments: Dry direct seeded rice (DD), Seedling transplanted by rice transplanter (ST), Wet direct seeded rice (WD) and Traditional/Manual transplanting (TT). The treatments were taken from 2 different areas, and for each area there were 3 replicates.

FieldMap: not done for this case study.

Eddy Covariance Flux measurements: not done for this case study

Montado/Dehesa (Portugal and Spain):

Soil microbial sampling: Satellite-based methods were used to indicate sampling points in two different countries: Portugal and Spain. Each country had a selection of three different farms, each with treatments having high, medium, and low density of animal presence (e.g., sheep, cows, and pigs).

FieldMap: During the autumn of 2022, in situ forest and biodiversity measurement work was carried out, which will provide ground truth information to other techniques used, such as remote sensing, in three pilot farms in Extremadura (Spain), and in three pilot farms in Portugal. FieldMap technology is used to measure plant biodiversity and existing biomass, obtain the main tree height diameter model, and generate the information needed to transform the C stored in the biomass into C values, in the six pilot farms, with agrosilvopastoral management, of this typical agro-ecosystem in the West of the Iberian Peninsula.

Eddy Covariance Flux measurements: not done for this case study.

Table 2. Summary of main results of in-situ measurements data.

CS No.	Case study	Country	Microbial Results		Forest biomass and biodiversity results	Eddy covariance results
			Soil Health indicators	Microbial C sequestration		
1	Agroforestry	The Netherlands	<p>Bacillus: no differences between agroforestry and control</p> <p>Plant growth promoting: no differences between agroforestry and control</p> <p>Mycorrhiza: no differences between agroforestry and control</p> <p>N cycle: higher nitrification activity in the trees of agroforestry in comparison with grasslands of the agroforestry system.</p>	<p>Methane emissions: no differences between agroforestry and control</p> <p>C sequestration: Presence of the trees in the agroforestry indicates higher C sequestration (genes) compared with the grassland of the agroforestry system.</p>	-	Data not available yet.
2	Peatland rewetting	The Netherlands	<p>Results Location 1:</p> <p>Bacillus: lower bacillus in the paludiculture areas than the degraded peatlands (control).</p> <p>Plant growth promoting: lower plant growth promoting bacteria in the paludiculture areas than the degraded peatlands (control).</p> <p>Mycorrhiza: no data available.</p> <p>N cycle: slightly higher nitrification and denitrification and lower nitrogen fixation activity in the paludiculture areas than the degraded peatlands (control).</p> <p>Results from Location 2 (Onlanden) and Location 3 (Blaauzaam) are not available yet.</p>	<p>Results Location 1:</p> <p>Increase of methane emission and consumption functions in the paludiculture soils. Based on the ratio, there is a higher expression of genes related to methane consumption.</p> <p>C sequestration: Slightly higher carbon sequestration (genes) in the paludiculture areas than the degraded peatlands (control).</p>	-	Location 2: Data is collected from the collaboration with Wageningen University (WUR) and the results are not finalized yet.

CS No.	Case study	Country	Microbial Results		Forest biomass and biodiversity results	Eddy covariance results
			Soil Health indicators	Microbial C sequestration		
3	Forest Management	Germany	First samples collected but data not available yet (currently processing). Expected results: February, 2024		Definition of 3 forest stand strata in the case study forest in Lübeck. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stratum 1. Mainly broadleaved stand. • Stratum 2. Mixed broadleaved and coniferous stand. • Stratum 3. Mainly coniferous stand. Biomass volume for each of the three strata. Local regression models (diameter-height) for each of the representative forest species.	-
4	Reduced tillage	Switzerland	N/A			
5	Organic cropping	Switzerland	N/A			
6	Fire forest management	Venezuela	N/A			
7	Eddy Covariance Flux measurements	Burkina Faso*	Data not available yet Expected results: April, 2024		-	-
8	Eddy Covariance Flux	South Africa	-	-	-	Data is collected and the results are not finalized yet.

CS No.	Case study	Country	Microbial Results		Forest biomass and biodiversity results	Eddy covariance results
			Soil Health indicators	Microbial C sequestration		
	measurements					
9	Integrated soil fertility management	Kenya	<p>Bacillus: decrease of Bacillus with the addition of farmyard manure (FYM) compared to control.</p> <p>Plant growth promoting: lower in the treatments of FYM with no chemical fertilization compared to control.</p> <p>Mycorrhiza: no data</p> <p>N cycle: Higher abundance of bacteria that acts in nitrification and denitrification pathways with the addition of FYM without chemical fertilization.</p>	<p>Methane emission: There is higher methane emission with the addition of FYM especially when it is added together with chemical fertilization.</p> <p>C sequestration: Higher abundance of bacteria that fixes C with the addition of FYM specially without the addition of chemical fertilization.</p>	-	-
10	Afforestation/peatland rewetting	Canada	First samples collected but data not available yet (currently processing). Expected results: February, 2024		-	-
11	Biochar	Sweden	N/A			
12	Biogas	Indonesia	<p>Results Location 1:</p> <p>Bacillus: non-organic arabica, organic arabica and the plant pongamia showed highest abundance of this genus compared to robusta and cacao.</p> <p>Plant growth promoting: non-organic arabica, organic arabica, cacao and the plant pongamia showed higher presence of plant growth promoting bacteria.</p> <p>Mycorrhiza: Pongamia showed higher abundance of arbuscular mycorrhiza while non-organic arabica showed increase of endomycorrhiza.</p> <p>N cycle: Soils with pongamia showed higher abundance of bacteria related to the N cycle as nitrate respiration and denitrification.</p>	<p>Results Location 1:</p> <p>Methane emissions: High tendency of methanotrophy for non-organic arabica and higher abundance of methylotrophic organisms in the soils with Pongamia</p> <p>C sequestration: non-organic arabica, organic arabica and the plant pongamia indicate higher C sequestration.</p> <p>Location 2: Data not available yet.</p>	-	-

CS No.	Case study	Country	Microbial Results		Forest biomass and biodiversity results	Eddy covariance results
			Soil Health indicators	Microbial C sequestration		
			Location 2: Data not available yet.			
13	Agroforestry	Spain	<p>Bacillus: rows with trees have the highest abundance of Bacillus, while rows with shrubs have the lowest.</p> <p>Plant growth promoting: results depend on the area. Area C showed lower plant growth promoting bacteria between trees and shrubs.</p> <p>Mycorrhiza: Arbuscular mycorrhiza are more frequent in between trees while ectomycorrhizal in the shrubs and trees rows.</p> <p>N cycle: the results are area variable and dependent on the area.</p>	<p>Methane emission: very low and no differences between treatments</p> <p>C sequestration: Trees rows and in between trees showed intermediate carbon sequestration when compared to forest and agriculture controls. The control of agriculture shows the highest emissions.</p>	<p>Definition of 5 forest stand strata, according to the year of planting (1996, 1998, 1999, 2002, 2005), in the three reforestation pilot farms in Extremadura.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mariblanca. ● Los Riscos. ● Carboneras. <p>Biomass volume for each strata (5) in the three pilot farms.</p> <p>Local regression models (diameter-height) for each of the representative forest species.</p>	-
14	Sustainable coffee and pepper production	Vietnam	N/A			
15	Sustainable rice production	Nepal	<p>Bacillus: Wet direct seeded rice treatment showed higher abundance of this genus.</p> <p>Plant growth promoting: data not available yet.</p> <p>Mycorrhiza: data not available yet.</p>	<p>Methane emission: data not available yet</p> <p>C sequestration: data not available yet</p>	-	-

CS No.	Case study	Country	Microbial Results		Forest biomass and biodiversity results	Eddy covariance results
			Soil Health indicators	Microbial C sequestration		
			N cycle: data not available yet.			
16	Montado/ Dehesa	Portugal & Spain	<p>Results of location 2:</p> <p>Bacillus: The medium intensity showed the higher presence of Bacillus.</p> <p>Plant growth promoting: High growth promoting bacteria in the presence of animals</p> <p>Mycorrhiza: lower arbuscular mycorrhiza and endomycorrhiza in the high intensity animals treatments</p> <p>N cycle: Lower nitrogen fixation in the treatment with high intensity of animals</p>	<p>Methane emission: higher methane emission for the high intensity animal presence treatments.</p> <p>C sequestration: There is a tendency that the high intensity animals have a lower C fixation capacity.</p>	<p>Definition of the monitoring area, dominated by trees, for each of the six pilot farms, three in Spain and three in Portugal.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dehesilla Alta (Spain). • Dehesa de Montehermoso. (Spain). • Montemoheda (Spain). • Herdade dos Padres. (Portugal). • Herdade do Azinhal. (Portugal). • Herdade dos Grous. (Portugal). <p>Biomass volume in the six pilot farms.</p> <p>Local regression models (diameter-height) for each of the representative forest species.</p>	-
17	Palm oil	Colombia	N/A			
18	Organic farming	Ukraine*	Data not available yet Expected results: April, 2024		-	-
19	Forest fire	Australia	N/A		N/A	Found strong correlation between monthly GPP and satellite-based SIF retrieved from TROPOMI over the

CS No.	Case study	Country	Microbial Results		Forest biomass and biodiversity results	Eddy covariance results
			Soil Health indicators	Microbial C sequestration		
						Tumbarumba site (KNMI results).
20	Restoration	China	N/A			

*: Sampling will be done between the period of November and December 2023.

It is crucial to emphasize that the presented table represents only a subset of the extensive findings. Therefore, drawing definitive conclusions solely from this table would be inadvisable. Further in-depth analysis and consideration of additional details, not presented here, are necessary for a more accurate interpretation of the results.

4. Conclusions

The integration of diverse in-situ measurement techniques across various case studies represents an advancement in our understanding of Land-Based Mitigation Techniques (LMTs). These techniques have yielded a unique data on microbial processes, soil health, vegetation, and greenhouse gas fluxes, providing invaluable insights into the potential of LMTs to mitigate carbon emissions and foster sustainable land management.

In total, we have collected 14 datasets for microbial analysis across 10 case studies, alongside 18 physic-chemical datasets spanning 13 case studies, with an additional three case studies contributing FieldMap and eddy-covariance data. The complexity of managing these diverse datasets and the multiple disciplines -including soil science, silviculture, and atmospheric science- underscores the multifaceted nature of the research. This requires more interdisciplinary collaboration with both the scientific community and practitioners.

Our primary conclusion is that the outcomes are inherently case study or LMT-specific, emphasizing the direct influence of LMT activities on in-situ measurements, particularly in relation to soil processes. For instance, in paludiculture, a close examination of methane results for consumption and emission is essential. Similarly, the higher presence of animals in the Spanish and Portuguese case studies has observable effects on soil diversity and health.

Additionally, the results obtained by in-situ measure requires the dedicated support and collaboration of case study stakeholders; thus, this highlights the need for transdisciplinary research, bringing together researchers, practitioners, and land use managers to monitor and measure LMTs. Further scaling up of in-situ measurements for various LMTS requires long term collaboration with land managers and conveying results that are useful for both improving yields/ land management practices and reducing emissions.

Moving forward, the next steps involve delving into the correlations between the results obtained from different techniques and their practical applicability. Furthermore, we will address the data that has not yet been delivered, enhancing the comprehensiveness the research. These conclusions collectively underline the importance of multifaceted in-situ measurements in advancing LMTs, as they provide insights into the complex interplay between land management practices and soil health, vegetation, gas fluxes and carbon sequestration.

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